

The contribution of a mega-event to the tourism development of the host country

Abstract:

Purpose – The purpose of the research is to capture the short-term and long-term positive results from the organization of a mega-event in the tourism development of the host country. Individual objectives concern the economic, social and cultural effects of a mega sports event, the economic, environmental and social effects on tourism, as well as possible opportunities through the creation of new ones and the improvement of the existing sports and tourist infrastructure.

Design/methodology/approach – 1. What are the short-term benefits of organizing a mega-event in tourism? 2. What are the long-term benefits of organizing a mega-event in tourism (heritage of the tourism product)? The bibliographic review will be used methodologically to answer the research questions, through the use of secondary research sources.

Findings – The impact that major sporting events have is huge for the host countries, in terms of tourism and the revenue generated by visitors, the visibility that the country acquires, as well as the awareness of the people on issues related to its culture and culture. The benefits for the host country are many, both in the short and long term. **Research limitations/implications** – The results have shown that the benefits are varied, but further research is needed, with a focus on the environmental footprint and sustainable practices applied to such events.

Practical implications – The aspect of usefulness of the research will provide information about the real results of organizing a popular mega-event, the opportunities it gives to the local community, as well as the immediate financial benefits. Furthermore, it will highlight that the international tourism industry has recently intensified its efforts, so that sports tourism grows into a strategic factor in the reshaping and planning of a country's tourist traffic, with emphasis on the proper rational organization and future utilization of infrastructure.

Originality/value – The research becomes original, as it focuses on the organization of a mega-event and the positive impact it had on levels of tourist demand, despite the adversity generated by the fact of the terrorist attack.

Keywords: Mega-events; Giga-events; heritage; financial benefits; tourist infrastructure; sustainability.

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1. Introduction

Sports tourism is an important alternative form of tourism with increasing importance for the promotion of a country and its ranking in a privileged position in the global list of the most popular tourist destinations. At the same time, it is a strong incentive for investments in modern sports structures but also in the upgrading of existing tourist structures, thus contributing to economic development (Wright, 2016). In recent years, there has been an increase in competitiveness among countries aspiring to host major sporting events.

However, taking on an event is an expensive and time-consuming process. The host city/country is called upon to engage in a continuous struggle to create and maintain those favorable conditions that will ensure the continuous development and strengthening of the heritage of the event (Leal de Oliveira et al., 2020). In some cases, the phenomenon of a country's inability to maintain its attractiveness as a tourist destination after the incident is observed. Therefore, it becomes necessary to continuously upgrade the tourist product, create new tourist infrastructure, as well as maintain it.

An example of a successful mega-event and its corresponding contribution to the development of sports tourism was the organization of UEFA Euro 2016 in France, amid terrorist attacks, which was hosted in thirteen cities. In fact, in 2016 France was the most popular European destination, due to the increase in (besoccer.com, 2017) tourism in several French cities, which hosted sports activities. Regarding the heritage of the event in the country and its possible utilization for additional economic and tourist development, the investments made in sports facilities are indicative.

2. The tourism impact of mega events in host countries

Major sporting events are social events that attract billions of spectators around the world and are sponsored by the world's most powerful transnational corporations (Grix and Lee, 2013). In this context, states compete with each other in terms of sports, economics and soft power exercise. By undertaking such manifestations, host countries expect to project their identity and specific cultural characteristics, their technological and economic power, to increase their credibility on the world stage, as well as their tourist inflows (Grix & Lee, 2013). The organizational developments that take place, significantly increase the value of the destination and its attractiveness. World major sporting events, such as the Olympic Games or the Football World Cup are an occasion and fertile ground for host countries to create a positive image, but the inability to take advantage of the opportunities presented may affect them (Giulianotti, 2015).

The allure of hosting a mega-event has increased significantly over the last two decades (Rowe & Baker, 2012). The advent of professionalism in sports, coupled with the world's highest per capita income and improvements in transmission technology, made mega-events a truly global experience, but countries and regions increasingly see these events as potential lucrative opportunities, encompassing great potential tangible and intangible benefits for the host (Horne & Manzenreiter, 2004).

The example of the Olympic Games is suitable for studying the short- and long-term benefits that the host country reaps. In particular, it is the main reason why cities/countries "need" mega events (Nooij et al., 2013). Creating an identity for a city/country is essentially a marketing strategy, which aims to highlight all its positive characteristics and strengthen its economy (Gratton & Preuss, 2008). Building this identity through hosting major sporting events can be complex and costly, but it is also effective due to the attractiveness and popularity of sporting events and the subsequent interest of investors and companies (Warren, 2018).

In a globalized environment, the possibilities that the organisation of major sporting events can offer for the host country are not limited to the economic sphere, but take on wider and varied implications (Müller, 2015b). Tourism is one of the world's leading growth sectors

in the service industry. Although many factors influence its development, one of the most noticeable contributions comes from world sporting events. In this context, countries around the world want to host such events in order to improve their position in the world rankings and exercise soft power.

An example of the use of Olympic diplomacy as a tool of soft power was the opening ceremony in China, which was used as a "showcase", with the aim of presenting the country's rich history and success to the world (Berkowitz et al. , 2007). China presented itself as an emerging state, so as to enhance its communication dynamics in the media (Ni, 2008). In particular, Olympic diplomacy focused on demonstrating China's economic progress, through the promotion of a technologically advanced organization of the Olympic Games and above all a country that is politically stable, as well as sensitive to addressing environmental issues by promoting the "Green Olympics" (Beyer, 2006). Alongside foreign policy goals, Olympic diplomacy was also used to consolidate China's nationalism, with the government or its government gaining more popularity and support (Luša, 2017).

Also of particular interest are the countries that, through hosting mega-events, expect to improve their economy and strength, which are characterized as emerging economies (Rosado & Paul, 2017). Despite the criticism and competition brought about by the division of countries into emerging and non-emerging, the role of major sporting events in their promotion and development is unquestionable. A typical example is South Africa, a country that hosted the football World Cup in 2010. When hosting mega-events, other opportunities were born for the economies of emerging countries, such as through trade and business deals made (Bravo et al., 2018). In addition to establishing partnerships, creating a positive image and strengthening the economy fosters a sense of security in potential visitors (Deffner & Labrianidis, 2005). In fact, those who choose to visit the country to watch the sports closely, will advertise and promote its culture and civilization (Lepp & Gibson, 2011).

2.1 Short-term benefits of holding a mega-event for the host country

Research on the impact of sports mega events is extensive and focuses mainly on economic outcomes such as individual income, employment and taxable business sales (Hotchkiss et al., 2003). However, only short-term economic benefits are often found. The focus of the studies is on the hospitality and tourism sector, as mega events promote the tourism market and international arrivals, which increase during their conduct (Vierhaus, 2019). In anticipation of these tourist inflows, host countries are often required to increase their investments, prior to the event, in hotels or infrastructure, such as the beautification of the city, the construction and expansion of stadiums, the upgrading physical and digital infrastructure and building entertainment areas (Dollinger et al., 2010).

Numerous studies focus on individual manifestations, and empirically, the evidence remains mixed. For example, Depken and Stephenson (2018) found that sports competitions increase hotel bookings, but Depken and Fore (2020) argued that there was no significant change in revenue or served customers in catering and accommodation. However, short-term capacity constraints may reduce any potential benefits, especially when it comes to seasonal events or individual games (Porter, 2000). Thus, in order to reap additional benefits, the construction of additional infrastructure capacity may be required. This is true even when major sporting events are hosted in cities with an organised transport network or modernised infrastructure. As presented by Baumann and Matheson (2018), Rio de Janeiro had to build 15,000 new hotel rooms for the 2016 Olympics despite the fact that it was already an established and popular tourist destination (Baade et al., 2021).

At the same time, when the United States hosted the FIFA World Cup, using income as a substitute for the amount of economic activity, 13 cities hosting the event, actually accumulated net losses during this period (Baade et al., 2021). In addition, Tien, Lo and Lin (2011) showed that based on a sample of 24 summer and winter Olympics, there is only weak

evidence that hosting a mega event is financially beneficial. The findings suggest that the resulting benefits are only identified during pre-Olympics preparation and are short-lived. Confirming this finding, Billings and Holladay (2012) showed limited evidence supporting any long-term effects of hosting the Olympics. Moreover, Lamla, Straub and Girsberger (2014) did not see significant economic benefits at macroeconomic level when investigating the impact of the 2008 European Football Championship in Switzerland.

On the other hand, Rose and Spiegel (2011) showed that mega event hosts are enjoying a permanent increase in commercial opening. The majority of studies looking at the impact of hosting a major sporting event focus on the event itself and in fact after the event. This is perhaps why there seems to be a lack of data highlighting a positive effect of hosting such an event. Confirming this, Brückner and Papa (2015) found that hosting the Olympics leads to a positive impact on economic growth. This *ex ante* effect causes an increase in investment and production both in the short and long term for the future host. However, there are still advantages, albeit in the short term, for 'failed candidates'. Given the weak evidence of the positive impact of mega events on traditional measures of economic activity, research has, again, focused on the results of the service sector resulting from sports tourists (Jones and Ponzini, 2018).

As for sports competitions, the scale of international visitors is much larger, as is the length of their stay. In particular, the 2014 football World Cup in Brazil increased tourist arrivals by about a million visitors, while only 100,000 international tourists arrived for the summer summer 2016 Olympic Games in Rio de Janeiro. In combination with the above data, Li et al. (2013) showed a significant increase in international visitors to Beijing in 2008, however, their numbers were limited due to the lengthy process of obtaining an entry visa to attend the Beijing Olympics, which may have discouraged further sports tourists from attending (Li & Song, 2013). Proponents of organizing the Olympics state that during the event, these tourist arrivals create a significant increase in both hotel occupancy and local retail (Rudkin & Sharma, 2020).

The research findings largely support this view, as Porter and Fletcher (2008) presented that hotel occupancy increased both during the Summer Olympics in Atlanta, but also during the Salt Lake City Winter Olympics. On the other hand, the 2006 FIFA World Cup in Germany caused an increase of about 700,000 additional hotel nights by foreigners, but no impact was found during the 1998 World Cup in France. Nevertheless, there is insufficient support that these increases in tourist arrivals are permanent. Dansero and Puttilli (2010) claimed that although the number of tourists increased in the city of Turin and its metropolitan area after the 2006 Winter Games, this increase was short-lived. Similarly, Solberg and Preuss (2007) showed that the Sydney Olympics resulted in a brief increase in tourism, but this was followed by a prolonged period of stagnation (Allmers & Maennig, 2009). To capitalize on the greater profits from these sports tourists, businesses in the host area can increase their investments before the event, to maximize future profits (Dollinger et al., 2010).

Such a way would be through the construction of additional infrastructure usually associated with hosting major sporting events. These upgrades are not limited to sports facilities (Kontokosta, 2012). They also include improvements to general infrastructure, such as reconstruction throughout the city, strengthening of transport and telecommunications infrastructure and construction of hotels, bars, restaurants and entertainment areas (Dollinger et al., 2010). The level of this infrastructure development may vary between cities, but the demands for investment are still high (Gratton & Solberg, 2007). Moreover, even if visitors increase in the short term and only around the mega event itself, it can be expected that investments and profits at the enterprise level will increase (Kaplanidou et al., 2016).

Exploring the enterprises located in the industrial sector is both interesting and vital, as they are often involved in the manufacture of intermediate goods needed to organize mega

events. For example, manufacturing companies may undertake to provide inputs for new hotels and stadiums or provide furniture and equipment for restaurants and bars (Davis, 2020). Other enterprises can support these efforts by providing telecommunications, metallurgical construction, textiles, petrochemicals, minerals and mechanical components. In addition, the technology sector may provide products and services to ensure appropriate levels of security throughout the timeframe. Compared to seasonal events, where tourists return every year, the demand for the host area may never be as great as it was during the mega events event. These problems are exacerbated when event stadiums fail to be reused and become known as "white elephants" (Davis, 2020).

2.2 Long-term benefits of hosting major sporting events

The long-term benefits of hosting major sporting events for host countries are also very important. In particular, through the hosting of international sports organisations, countries can emerge as custodians of a world heritage (Luša, 2017). In this way they exert attraction, highlighting the truths they desire and gaining new momentum. In a connected and competitive world, hosting Mega Events can be a soft power exercise tool, significantly affecting the global landscape. Clearly, the benefits are not limited to tourism, since the preparation for sports competitions requires the movement of athletes, finding sponsors, entering into partnerships, etc. (Fan, 2010). Throughout this process of organization and management, a fundamental element is the strategies used, among them the branding of the host country/city (Luša, 2017). In other words, hosted sporting events and other events become an opportunity to connect the city with the characteristics and values of the event (Fan, 2008).

City branding is a strategy that finds application in many fields and is now largely used by states (Bjerke & Naess, 2021). According to Lynch (1960) identity is the degree to which a person can recognize or recall a place, differentiating it from others. Each city has a unique identity, which consists of images and memories that are either negative or positive. The image of the city essentially consists in terms of urban elements, such as monumental buildings, public spaces and other special features. From a general point of view, city branding is mainly based on three main characteristics, which are the image, uniqueness and authenticity. Almost every city has city branding on its agenda in order to reshape its image (Kapelioti, 2019).

Kotler et al. (1996) argue, in fact, that places are products whose identities and values must be designed and marketed, like other commercial products. According to Ashworth (2009) one of the goals of branding of the city or place is to discover or create uniqueness, which makes the city different from the others. The main goal in the manufacture of brands for cities is the articulation of the city in the globalized world. For a city to develop successfully, it needs economic wealth and an attractive image. Thus, the branding of the city should deal with how culture and history, economic and social development, infrastructure and architecture, landscape and environment, among other things, can be combined into a marketable identity that is acceptable to all people (Zhang, 2011).

As a holistic approach, city branding serves as a promotional tool for creating a unique image of a city. The ultimate goal is to attract expanded population groups, mainly including potential visitors from outside the country and enabling them to perceive and positively evaluate its culture. Achieving this goal requires the involvement of different parties or actors and of course careful long-term planning (Bjerke & Naess, 2021). In this context, major sporting events are suitable for supporting these goals, however, as the scale and requirements of the branding manufacturing process grow, so do the potential opportunities and threats to the country (Kavaratzis & Hatch, 2013).

A recent example concerns Qatar, which will host the World Football Championship in 2022 (Al-Emadi et al., 2017). There were many opportunities for the country, which

contributed to strengthening its negotiating capacity and position in international relations. However, since the announcement of the hosting of this great sporting event by Qatar, there have been reports of poor working conditions of people who mainly arrived in the country from India, Pakistan, Nepal for the construction of sports facilities. Press reports said more than 4,000 people had lost their lives working for the Cup preparation projects in Qatar (Zumi, 2020).

Major sporting events, such as the FIFA Olympics or World Cups, have been used by host countries to promote their values and communicate them to domestic and global audiences (Preuss, 2007). These experiences support the transfer of the special characteristics that the nation stands for and thus contribute to the strengthening of the country's "brand", differentiating it from others. This process mainly includes corporate branding, public management and cultural geography (Hereźniak & Florek, 2018). For this reason, all the above characteristics and elements that appear each time on the occasion of hosting major sporting events have been linked to the emergence of the country as a model, enabling it to introduce new policies, directly or indirectly. In fact, intangible results create in the long run many more opportunities and benefits for the country hosting the games and are a legacy for national and world sport itself (Cornelissen, 2008).

However, undertaking an event is a costly process in terms of resources and time. The host city/country is called upon to engage in a constant struggle to create and maintain those favorable conditions, which will ensure the continuous development and strengthening of the heritage of the event (Chen et al., 2013). In some cases, the phenomenon of a country's inability to maintain its attractiveness as a tourist destination after the event is observed. So, it becomes necessary to constantly upgrade the tourism product, create new tourist infrastructure, as well as maintain them. Hosting a major sporting event and increasing tourism does not guarantee that revenues will be kept at the same level for the country (Müller, 2015a). Barcelona, Seoul and Atlanta experienced an increase in hotel occupancy before the Olympics, but also a decrease in average occupancy during the Olympic year, as well as in the first years after the Games. Barcelona saw revenues drop by almost 60% in the next 2 years after the Games (McKay & Plumb, 2001). Barcelona's strategy was to use the Olympic Games to create the image of the cultural city. Although the number of tourists continued to grow, it was not enough to balance the reconstruction costs spent on hotel accommodation. Lillehammer, on the other hand, is an example where unrealistic optimism has caused overinvestment in the local hotel sector (Teigland, 1999). Although tourism increased after the Games, it was not enough to balance the increase in supply. As a result, there have been several bankruptcies in the tourism industry.

In recent years, the competition to host a large sporting event has led to great competition, because the number of reception applicants has increased. Thus, the creation of stadiums and other sports facilities does not guarantee that the destination will be elected as the host of major sporting events in the future. In particular, there is talk of the co-organization of the 2030 World Cup by Greece, Egypt and Saudi Arabia, while other countries have submitted similar proposals. Starting in 2026, the World Cup will expand into a 48-team tournament, likely requiring some nations to work together to host an event of this size. With Asia hosting in 2022 (Qatar) and North America in 2026 (USA, Canada and Mexico), it leaves the opportunity to welcome 2030 to Africa, Europe and South America. The Oceania region does not have the infrastructure for a 48-team World Cup, especially after Australia joined the Asian confederation (Borg, 2022).

The intention of the countries to take over the World Cup, even through co-organization, reveals the recognition of the benefits that accompany hosting a major sporting event (Borg, 2022). In addition to the investments that will be made in infrastructure and the attraction of visitors from the countries involved, the long-term benefits emerge equally important. Among them are the collaborations at the level of tourism, business and of course

the formation of a cooperation framework to achieve a common interest that will benefit the co-organizing countries (Bjerke & Naess, 2021). Even if this creates import leaks that reduce the benefits to the local economy, it is nevertheless a smart strategy, going beyond potential long-term demand.

2.3 The example of the UEFA Euro 2016 competition in France

An example of a successful mega-event and its corresponding contribution to the development of sports tourism was the organization of UEFA Euro 2016 in France, amid terrorist attacks, which was hosted in thirteen cities, contributing 1.2 billion euros to the country's revenue, with 51% of them being revenues from tourism. In fact, in 2016 France became the most popular European destination, due to the increases in several French cities, which hosted sports activities. Regarding the heritage of the event in the country and its possible use for additional economic and tourist development, the investments made in sports facilities are indicative (besoccer.com, 2017).

In particular, France welcomed 1,216,000 visitors throughout the tournament, of which 70% French and 30% foreign, exceeding the expectations of the organizers. In addition, the experience of the Fan Zone turned out to be very positive: a survey of the general public shows a satisfaction rate of 92%, with no noticeable differences between age groups or nationalities. The balance sheet is also positive, as for the protection of the city, since no damage was caused to shops, nor were there any public disturbances. The accompanying programme implemented by the City of Paris, with 400,000 beneficiaries, resulted in the organisation of 84 events in various districts, including 14 art installations (Borg, 2022). At the same time, Paris drastically reduced the environmental impact of the tournament. The deputy mayor pointed out that France was the first mega event country to receive the ISO 20121 certification, which is the most demanding in the world in terms of environmental conservation. More than 160 actions were directed in this direction: from the eco-design of modular structures to the sorting and recycling of 132 tons litter collected (Borg, 2022).

In terms of tourism impact, for the first time, Paris has regained a level of tourist traffic similar to that it had before last November's attacks. The number of visitors in June 2016 was 1 to 2% higher than in June 2015, with the increase mainly due to European visitors. Revenues from tourism amounted to 625.8 million euros, with 35% coming from accommodation, 30% from restaurants and food services, 20% from purchases and visits and 15% from the transport sector. In the communications part of UEFA's hospitality, the Eiffel Tower Fan Zone welcomed more than 3,100 journalists who filmed around 6,000 reports broadcast to 100 million viewers in more than 100 different countries. As for posts on social networks, these totaled more than 17 million views (sportsbiz.co.ke, 2017).

3. Methodology

3.1 Purpose and objectives of the investigation

Purpose is at the core of research, as it encapsulates the central theme around which it develops, while defining the direction in which it moves. Based on the purpose, the research questions and research objectives are then formulated (Creswell, 2012). Therefore, it is necessary to be clear, predetermined and specific, in order to create the appropriate questions, which will then be answered through research. In this way, the resulting data will be measurable and usable, while they are expected to help in the development of the study and in the enrichment of the subject under investigation.

In this case, the purpose of the research was to capture the short- and long-term positive effects of the organization of a mega-event on the tourism development of the host countries and especially France, as the host country of UEFA Euro 2016. Specific objectives relate to

the economic, social and cultural effects of a mega sports events, the economic, environmental and social impacts on tourism, as well as possible opportunities through the creation of new and the improvement of existing sports and tourism infrastructure.

3.2 Research Questions

The effectiveness of the research concerns both the goals and the questions that will be asked, as well as the answer to them, through the conclusions that will emerge (Creswell, 2012). Based on the data of this research, the research questions are defined as follows:

1. What are the short-term benefits of organizing a mega-event in tourism?
2. What are the long-term benefits of organizing a mega-event in tourism (heritage of the tourist product)?

To answer the research questions, the literature review was methodologically used, through the use of secondary research sources.

3.3 Originality and usefulness of research

The originality and uniqueness of a survey lies in the content or methods it uses. It is important for a study to be characterized as original, because in this way new parameters and characteristics in a subject are studied and thus new evidence arises or older conclusions are questioned. This process evolves both thinking and methodology, as well as research objects (Creswell, 2012).

In the case of France, as the host country of a mega event, the research becomes original, since it focuses on the organization of a mega-event and the positive impact it had on levels of tourist demand, despite the adversities created by the fact of the terrorist attack. The usefulness of the survey will provide information on the actual results of organizing a popular mega-event, the opportunities it gives to the local community, as well as the immediate economic benefits. It will also highlight that the international tourism industry has recently intensified its efforts so that sports tourism becomes a strategic factor in the reconfiguration and planning of a country's tourist traffic, with emphasis on proper rational organization and future utilization of infrastructure.

3.4 Results - Proposals for further research

The literature review that took place highlighted important data on the research on the tourist benefits of hosting a mega event. In particular, through the research used, it became clear that the short-term benefits are not limited only to the country's revenue, the increase in accommodation occupancy or the promotion of its brand, but include a number of obvious and invisible aspects. For example, the examination of the impact on industrial enterprises has largely been ignored, while the numerous studies focus on individual manifestations, and empirically, the evidence remains mixed. Still, the majority of studies examining the impact of hosting a major sporting event focus on the event itself (Kaplanidou et al., 2016). Therefore, there appears to be value in considering the above parameters.

In terms of the long-term benefits of hosting a mega event for a country, hosted sporting events and other events become an opportunity to connect the city with the characteristics and values of the event (Fan, 2008). Each city has a unique identity, which consists of images and memories that are either negative or positive. Thus, it becomes necessary to constantly upgrade the tourist product, create new tourist infrastructure, as well as maintain them. In the example of France, which has been studied, a new, interesting aspect of the environmental impact and opportunities for the host country has emerged. In particular, Paris drastically reduced the environmental impact of the tournament. The deputy mayor pointed out that France was the first country to organize mega events, which received the ISO 20121 certification, which is the most demanded in the world in terms of environmental conservation. More than 160 actions were directed in this direction: from the eco-design of

modular structures to the sorting and recycling of the 132 tons of waste collected (Borg, 2022).

It is concluded that the present literature review has brought to light gaps and omissions of previous research, while highlighting points that should be explored in future studies. At the same time, he underlined the importance of sustainability, as a concept that must be inextricably linked to the organization of a major sporting event. Through the case study of France, the importance was highlighted, not only of examining the environmental footprint that a major sporting event leaves in the host country, but also of the actions it must take to protect citizens, guests and future generations. It is important that major sporting events, such as the Olympic Games or UEFA event, are aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals as set by the United Nations. In fact, the IOC identifies as a priority social development and sustainability, which can be achieved or even promoted through sport. The conditions caused by the pandemic have given rise to innovations, which are expected to be further developed in the future. France's hosting of UEFA was a fertile ground and an opportunity to implement sustainable solutions. The challenge is to continue to apply similar practices in future sporting events, so that they become an axis and an example for all countries (Tzavaras, 2021).

4. References

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